

The Photo-reduction of Alcoholic Solutions of Ferric Chloride in Light.

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Benrath (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1905, 72, 220) has studied the photo-reduction of ferric chloride dissolved in methyl and ethyl alcohols in sun light by measuring the density of the solution at different intervals during exposure to light. The photo-reduction in sun light is more rapid than that in the artificial light so much so that crystals of ferrous sulphate separate out from a concentrated solution of ferric sulphate exposed to sun light (*cf. Benrath, Z. phys. Chem.*, 1910, 74, 115).

Prasad and Sohoni (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 489) have studied the photo-reduction of ferric chloride dissolved in methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohols in artificial light and have examined the effect of the intensity of the incident light on solutions of different concentrations. They find that in solution in perfectly anhydrous alcohols, the photo-reduction tends to reach a stationary stage but the addition of even slight amount of water causes a reversal of the reaction.

In the following investigation the photo-reduction of ferric chloride dissolved in the above named alcohols has been studied in artificial light for a longer time than that required to reach the equilibrium stage and the order of the photo-reduction has been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The Order of the Photo-reduction of Ferric Chloride in Artificial Light.

A 1000-Watt Philip's lamp was used as the source of light and the intensity was kept constant by means of a variable resistance placed in series with the lamp. The beam of light rendered parallel by a lens was first passed through a cell (4 cm. thick) containing distilled water to remove the heat radiations before it was incident

on the cell (20 mm. \times 50 mm.) made of optical glass, used to contain the ferric chloride solution. The intensity of the incident light was measured by a Ruben's thermopile connected to a Broca galvanometer and it could be varied by interposing piles of glass plates in the path of the beam.

The solutions were prepared by dissolving B.D.H. anhydrous ferric chloride in Kahlbaum's or Merck's extra pure alcohols which were further purified in the laboratory according to standard methods. 3.5 c.c. of the solution were placed in the reaction cell which was closed by a rubber stopper carrying syphon tubes to remove the solution; the ends of the tubes were closed by pinch cocks and the stopper was made air-tight by coating it with methylated collodion.

The cell was then exposed to light for a certain time at room temperature (28-29°). The optical homogeneity of the solution was maintained by gently shaking it during exposure to light as done by Ghosh and Purkayastha (*J. Indian Chem.*, 1929, 6, 827) and Prasad and Sohoni (*loc. cit.*). The reduction of ferric chloride was determined by titrating the solution with *N*/100-potassium dichromate using diphenylamine as an internal indicator (*cf.* Knopp, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 253). The volume in c.c. of the dichromate solution required to oxidise the volume of the indicator was first determined and this quantity was subtracted from each titration reading. The effect of alcohols and aldehydes on the titration of ferric salts by potassium dichromate was also studied and a small correction was applied for the presence of alcohols.

In the following tables *T*, *X* and *K* denote the time in minutes, the reduction of ferric chloride in milli moles and the zero-molecular constant respectively. The asterisk (*) in the following tables indicates the stationary state for which the velocity constants have not been calculated.

TABLE I.

Solution in pure methyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.118M.		Intensity = 7.4 cm.							
<i>T</i> /60	...	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
<i>X</i> $\times 10^2$...	2.85	6.15	9.2	12.2	12.35	13.55	16.25	—
<i>K</i> $\times 10^4$...	4.75	5.13	5.0	5.1	4.12	3.8	3.87	—

TABLE II.

Solution in pure anhydrous ethyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.115M		Intensity = 25 cm.								
$T/60$...	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
$X \times 10^3$...	2.25	4.45	6.5	5.9	5.25	7.55	8.65	10.35	12.05
$K \times 10^4$...	3.77	3.73	3.61	*	*	2.01	2.06	2.17	2.24

TABLE III.

Solution in n-propyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.16 M.		Intensity = 7.5 cm.									
$T/60$...	1	2	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	6	7	8
$X \times 10^3$...	1.8	3.1	4.85	5.85	6.5	7.05	7.55	8.45	9.36	10.41
$K \times 10^4$...	3.0	2.51	2.69	2.78	2.71	2.61	2.52	2.31	2.23	2.18

TABLE IV.

Solution in n-butyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.15 M.		Intensity = 25 cm.								
$T/60$...	1	2	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	6	
$X \times 10^3$...	1.8	3.15	4.91	5.65	5.85	6.35	7.85	8.65	
$K \times 10^4$...	1.3	2.6	2.73	2.7	2.62	2.4	

The curves obtained on plotting X against T are shown in Fig. 1. It will be seen that each curve consists of two straight lines separated from each other. This indicates that the photo-reduction proceeds in two stages and the order of the reaction is zero-molecular in both the stages. It is also apparent from the curves that the reaction proceeds faster in the first stage than in the second one.

FIG. 1.

Extinction Coefficients.

The extinction coefficients of solutions of ferric chloride undergoing reduction were measured in different parts of the visible spectrum with a view to see (a) if any complexes or intermediate compounds of ferric chloride are formed and (b) if any change in the absorption of light by the solution takes place. Nutting's spectrophotometer in conjunction with the Hilger wave-length spectrometer was used. Only solutions in methyl and ethyl alcohols have been examined as these give fairly good reduction on exposure to light.

TABLE V.

Solution in methyl alcohol.

Initial conc. of the solution = 0.15 M Intensity = 7.4 cm.

Time (hrs.)	E x t i n c t i o n c o e f f i c i e n t s f o r			
	6220Å	5800Å	5500Å	5300Å
1	0.00	0.16	0.28	0.4
2	0.00	0.12	0.18	0.28
3	0.00	0.115	0.175	0.26
4	0.00	0.11	0.17	0.255
5	0.00	0.04	0.12	0.20
6	0.00	0.01	0.08	0.15
8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13

TABLE VI.

Solution in anhydrous ethyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.18M. Intensity = 25 cm.

	E x t i n c t i o n c o e f f i c i e n t s f o r			
	6220Å	5800Å	5500Å	5300Å
1	0.16	0.22	0.30	0.37
2	0.16	0.21	0.28	0.34
3	0.15	0.22	0.30	0.34
4	0.16	0.22	0.295	0.34
5	0.16	0.22	0.30	0.34
6	0.11	0.17	0.23	0.26
7	0.11	0.15	0.20	0.23
8	0.06	0.10	0.15	0.18
10	0.04	0.06	0.095	0.12

The curve obtained on plotting the values of extinction coefficients against time (Fig. 3, Table V) as well as results in Table VI show that some remarkable change takes place in the solution after the reduction has reached a certain value.

*Effect of the Addition of Ferric Hydroxide Sol to the
Alcoholic Solutions of Ferric Chloride.*

It is known that hydrolysis of ferric chloride is considerably increased in light (*cf.* Dhar, "Chemical Action of Light," p. 381 ; and Ritche, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1269). It is probable in the present case that ferric chloride may undergo hydrolysis on account of the water formed during the progress of the reaction and this being in a colloidal state may influence the reduction of ferric chloride after some time. The reduction was, therefore, studied by adding 0.5 c.c. of pure ferric hydroxide sol. to 3.5 c.c. of the reaction mixture. The added amount of the sol did not cause any large change (i) in the concentration of the solution and (ii) in the absorption of light by the solution. To note the effect of the colloidal particles alone, a blank experiment was performed with the addition of 0.5 c.c. of distilled water to the ferric chloride solution.

In the following tables T denotes time in minutes, X_1 and X_2 reduction in millimoles of ferric chloride in the presence of water and the sol. respectively.

TABLE VII.

Solution in pure methyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.191M.		Intensity = 7.4 cm.					
$T/60$...	1	2	3	4	5	6
$X_1 \times 10^2$...	3.4	7.25	11.1	14.1	14.55	15.6
$X_2 \times 10^2$...	3.15	4.85	8.85	11.65	12.05	—

TABLE VIII.

Solution in anhydrous ethyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.095 M		Intensity = 7.4 cm.				
$T/60$...	1	2	3	4	5
$X_1 \times 10^2$...	1.9	3.75	5.35	5.35	6.15
$X_2 \times 10^2$...	1.65	3.25	4.45	4.45	5.25

TABLE IX.

Solution in n-propyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.165M.		Intensity = 7.4 cm.				
$T/60$...	1	2	3	4	5
$X_1 \times 10^2$...	1.55	4.15	7.15	8.35	10.15
$X_2 \times 10^2$...	1.35	3.55	5.35	6.45	8.25

TABLE X.

Solution in n-butyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.091 M.		Intensity = 7.4 cm.				
$T/60$...	1	2	3	4	5
$X_1 \times 10^2$...	1.35	4.85	7.85	8.95	10.45
$X_2 \times 10^2$...	1.15	3.35	5.25	6.65	8.45

It will be seen that the colloidal ferric hydroxide inhibits the reduction of ferric chloride and the amount of inhibition increases with the progress of the reduction. The inhibition may be caused by (i) the retarding influence of the colloidal ferric hydroxide or (ii) a diminution in the intensity of light absorbed by the solution due to the screening effect of the colloidal particles.

$X_1 - T$ and $X_2 - T$ curves are similar to each other. It, therefore, appears that colloidal ferric hydroxide does not exert any specific influence (a) in causing a change in the course of the reaction from the first to the second stage or (b) in the appearance of the flat part in the curves (Fig. 1) which may be the equilibrium state observed by Prasad and Sohony (*loc. cit.*).

Winther and Oxholt-Howe (*Z. Wiss. Phot.*, 1913, 14, 196), have advanced a theory that at least two different light absorbing molecular species containing ferric ions are present in solutions of ferric chloride in organic acids. As a tentative explanation, it may be considered probable that in the alcoholic solution of ferric chloride a complex containing ferric ion and having a small absorption coefficient is formed as the concentration of the organic substances in the solution increases in course of time. The photo-reduction of this complex or of ferric chloride in the presence of this complex follows a zero order as indicated in the second stage of the reaction.

Solution of FeCl₃ in MeOH.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

Solution of FeCl₃ in EtOH.

FIG. 4.

The extinction coefficient wave-lengths curves (Figs. 2 and 4) for different exposures of the reaction mixture to light are similar to each other. It appears that the solution containing the complex during the second stage of the reduction behaves towards the change of the extinction co-efficient with wave-lengths in the same way as before the complex is formed. Ghosh and collaborators have shown that the concentration of a complex formed in a photo-chemical reaction can be calculated if the extinction co-efficients of the reactants and of the complex be known. This, however, could not be done in the present case as a large number of substances are present in the solutions of ferric chloride in alcohols undergoing reduction and their concentrations are not known.

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